

TOPIC: Literature Survey in Software Engineering

TEACHER:

DATE: 17/03/2023.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
TITLE:	Tertiary Study about Requirements Engineering and Software to Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence
PARTICIPANTS:	
DESCRIPTION:	An overview of the state of the art of secondary studies on Requirements and Software Engineering for AI Systems Based on Machine Learning.
GENERAL OBJECTIVES:	Map requirements engineering activities applied to machine learning research in artificial intelligence systems.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION
1. What is the state of the art of requirements engineering for machine learning systems and what are the most researched topics in requirements engineering for machine learning?	Identify research and proposals regarding the use of requirements engineering for machine learning and artificial intelligence. Identify the main methods, techniques, proposals, uses and when and by whom they occurred, in addition to the supporting tools and roles involved in the use of requirements engineering for machine learning and artificial intelligence.
2. What are the challenges and gaps highlighted by the requirements engineering literature for machine learning and artificial intelligence?	Verify the challenges and possible paths for future research on requirements engineering for machine learning and artificial intelligence.

PICOC CRITERIA	
POPULATION:	Secondary studies published about requirements engineering
INTERVENTION:	Methods, tools, techniques, process, approach
COMPARISON:	Not applicable
RESULTS:	State of art about Requirements Engineering
CONTEXT:	Applied to artificial intelligence and machine learning search

IDENTIFICATION OF STUDIES	
SEARCH STRATEGY:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Automatic Search in Scientific Databases; 2. Forward Snowballing;
LIST OF SEARCH SOURCES:	<p>Automatic Search</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ACM DL: https://dl.acm.org/ 2. Engineering Village: engineeringvillage.com 3. IEEE Xplore: http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/ 4. Scopus: https://www.scopus.com/ 5. Web of Science: webofscience.com 6. Wiley: https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com
REASONS FOR CHOOSING OF SEARCH SOURCES:	<p>Automatic Search</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The source of studies must provide a search engine via the Web; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ that allows, at least, a search for the abstract or summary; ○ that allows the use of strings with support for Boolean expressions; ○ that produces the same results whenever the same string is entered; ○ that is capable of exporting search results to popular formats for tools to support systematic studies. ● The source of studies must index publication vehicles that have Computing as an end or means.
KEYWORDS:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● systematic mapping, systematic review, systematic literature mapping, systematic literature review, literature survey ● requirements engineering, requirements elicitation, requirements analysis, requirements specification, requirements validation, requirements management ● machine learning, artificial intelligence, data driven
STRING:	<p>(("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data-driven") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification" OR "requirements validation" OR "requirements management ") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey"))</p>
LANGUAGE:	English

SELECTION AND EVALUATION OF STUDIES

INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

IC: The secondary study identifies proposals, use or evaluation of requirements engineering research focused on machine learning or artificial intelligence;

EC1: Full text not available for free on the Web or on the CAPES Periódicos Platform;

EC2: Not written in English;

EC3: Not a secondary study;

EC4: Does not address requirements engineering for machine learning or artificial intelligence;

EC5: It is a preliminary or summarized version of another study already included;

QUALITY CRITERIA:

QC1: Are the inclusion criteria properly described?

2 - the criteria are explicit

1 - the criteria are implicit

0 - criteria are not defined or cannot be easily identified

QC2: Are the exclusion criteria properly described?

2 - the criteria are explicit

1 - the criteria are implicit

0 - criteria are not defined or cannot be easily identified

QC3: Does the search cover all relevant studies?

2 - (Uses four or more relevant databases) or (one search engine AND no extra search strategy)

1 - ((Uses three relevant sources) OR (a search engine)) AND (an extra search strategy)

0 - (uses a maximum of two relevant sources) E (no extra search strategy)

QC4: Is the quality of included primary studies assessed?

2 - quality criteria are explicit and associated with each primary study

1 - the secondary study research questions or selection criteria address the quality of the primary study

0 - quality assessment is not carried out or is not made explicit

QC5: Are primary studies adequately described?

	<p>2 - the details of each primary study are explicit 1 - there is only one summary of each study 0 - there are no results from the primary studies analyzed</p> <p>QC6: Is the justification for the study adequately described? 2 - the justification is duly substantiated and relevant studies are cited as related 1 - the justification is not clear or relevant studies are not cited 0 - justification is not cited and without relevant related studies</p> <p>QC7: Is the protocol validation properly described? 2 - a - strings are derived from the research questions; b - the data to be extracted is related to the research questions and c - the data analysis procedure is appropriate to answer the questions 1 - a, b or c are absent or not treated adequately 0 - validation is not described or cannot be easily inferred</p> <p>QC8: Is the extraction properly described and appropriate? 2 - a - extraction form is explicitly described; b - there is a strategy for extracting and recording data duly described; and c - how the data extraction process is carried out and validated 1 - a, b or c are absent or not treated adequately 0 - validation is not described or cannot be easily inferred</p>
STRATEGY TO SELECT STUDIES:	At this stage, the articles obtained are selected by applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria defined in this protocol. Each document will be assigned a status (included, excluded or doubtful) that will be analyzed by the supervisor. The selection will be carried out by three people, one of whom will be called in case of disagreement between the other two.
EVALUATION OF QUALITY STUDIES:	The evaluation table with the appropriate criteria, values and justifications is found at the end of this protocol. The evaluation strategy will be the application of the criteria during extraction, that is, in the phase in which the articles are read in full.
SYNTHESIS STRATEGY	
STRATEGY OF EXTRACTION DATA	After fully reading the studies, we seek to identify answers to the research questions and document them in an extraction table. The extraction will be carried out by three people, one of whom is a specialist in machine learning and artificial intelligence and supervised by a fourth person.
STRATEGY TO SUMMARIZATION OF RESULTS	Using the extraction table, analyzes must be carried out by listing the answers, calculating probabilities or odds ratios and constructing graphs to check the relevance of the results found. The analysis will be carried out by three people, two of them with experience in ER and one in ML and AI.

STRATEGY OF PUBLICATION

Once the results are all summarized and all readings and syntheses completed, a document will be created that summarizes and documents the results found that answer the questions in the format of a scientific article to be submitted to events and journals.

SEARCH

Date: 18/10/23

Source: Scopus

Applied to: palavras-chave, título e abstract

Results: 76

Source: ACM DL

Applied to: abstract

Results: 6

Source: IEEE XPlore

Applied to: command search

Resultados: 29

Source: Engineering Village

Applied to: sujeito, título e abstract

Results: 60

Source: Wiley

Applied to: abstract

	<p>Results: 1</p> <p>Source: Web of Science</p> <p>Applied to: abstract</p> <p>Results: 21</p>
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Pilot Test of String

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1pnpiJq84mrDebz5dsQMrdvPWBtsrnMnYtgT0Hzqa08M/edit?usp=sharing>

Inclusion and Exclusion of Studies

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1iHi-0D6yopFaotmf7O5iwy9IEzMB6FX4BCLMBcLH190/edit?usp=sharing>

Snowballing

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1iHi-0D6yopFaotmf7O5iwy9IEzMB6FX4BCLMBcLH190/edit?usp=sharing>

Extraction Form

- Title
- Authors
- Affiliation
- Publication vehicle
- Year of publication
- Publication type
- Search source
- Number of citations
- How many search sources
- What search strategies
- How many primary studies did you analyze?
- What is the objective of the secondary study Search string used in each secondary study What are the contributions of each secondary study
- What is the state of the art of requirements engineering for machine learning systems and what are the most researched topics in requirements engineering for machine learning? What are the contributions of RE in AI or ML studies (techniques, processes, tools, metrics)
 - What are the ER steps explored in AI or ML studies?

- What are the elicitation techniques explored in AI or ML studies?
- What are the analysis techniques explored in AI or ML studies?
- What are the most explored specification techniques in AI or ML studies?
- What validation techniques are explored in AI or ML studies?
- What are the management techniques explored in AI or ML studies?
- What are the tools that support RE in AI or ML studies?
- Do secondary studies point to specific data-driven RE approaches?
- What are the challenges and gaps highlighted by the requirements engineering literature for machine learning and artificial intelligence?
 - What is the reported maturity of primary ER studies applied to AI or ML?
 - What are the challenges identified in each secondary study?
 - Future work highlighted in each secondary study?

Extraction Form

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1tNQIJc8MPtggqQ3kXiFRtHp25RRW5YxmiUq2rsS65w/edit?usp=sharing>